

FIELD PESTS OF RICE AND THEIR MANAGEMENT PRACTICES BY “FADAMA” III PARTICIPATING FARMERS IN ABUJA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

A diagnostic survey assessing the status of rice pests, and their management strategies by the “Fadama” III participating farmers in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria was carried out. Data from the survey were collected from the 28 production clusters in the 10 Fadama Development Areas in the six Area Councils. Semi-structured interviews, farm diagnostic surveys, and specimens taken from rice that was afflicted with pests and disease were employed as the instruments. Armyworm, with a prevalence of 28.91%, was the insect pest species with the highest incidence among the respondents, according to the statistics. Weeds were viewed as the primary obstacle on a rice farm by the majority of the study's participants (56.67%). The plant most resistant to herbicide application was *Sacciolepis africana*, with a mean frequency of 28.43%. The farmers were more concerned about managing weeds, birds and rodents on the field, but had little or no concern for rice insect pests. To enable sustainable rice production in the FCT, the implementation of a rice pest management plan for the rice farmers such as regular monitoring of pests at various growth stages and Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices is a necessity.

Keywords: Abuja-Nigeria, Fadama, Incidence, Insect Pest, Integrated Pest Management (IPM), Rice, Weeds.

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.), Family Poaceae, is an important staple in Nigeria and a major cereal crop grown in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, Nigeria. It is one of the mandate crops by the FCT Fadama farmers under the Fadama III Additional Financing (AFI). Rice is used in the preparation of several local dishes that are eaten in every home, especially during festivals and ceremonies in Nigeria

(Seck *et al.*, 2012, Akinragbe, 2022). Nigeria may offer a clear comparative advantage in terms of increasing rice production for use as food, raw materials, or even export based on its current state of rice farming and ecological endowment (Erhie *et al.*, 2018).

The main objective of the Fadama project in Nigeria is to increase the incomes of Fadama users on a sustainable basis (Ani, 2014; Anjorin *et al.*, 2020). However, there were

various challenges mitigating against optimum derivable benefits, that the Fadama has the potential to provide (Gao *et al.*, 2023). To provide relevant management options for pests of rice and to enable optimum yield, there is a need to determine the status of rice production and the incidence of pests of the crop. This study assessed the knowledge and awareness of participating rice farmers and determine the incidence of insect pests, and weeds associated with rice farms in the FCT, Abuja. The findings from this study are expected to be useful in decision-making in future rice pest management planning and implementation.

METHODOLOGY

Study area

The research area is Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), in Nigeria's north central region. The FCT consists of six Area Councils: Abaji, AMAC, Bwari, Gwagwalada, Kuje, and Kwali. The survey was conducted in 10 Fadama Development Areas (FDA), as illustrated in Figure 1. It is located between Latitude $70^{\circ} 20' N$ and Longitudes $60^{\circ} 45'$ and $70^{\circ} 39' E$.

Figure 1. Map of FCT showing Fadama Development Areas within the Area Council. Source: FCT Fadama.

Data collection

Flexible semi-structured interviews, as well as diagnostic field surveys and assessments of rice fields, were used to conduct this study. This instrument was used to gather data on rice farming activities, respondents' knowledge of pests and illnesses that affect rice farms, and their level of IPM practice. Twenty (20) questionnaires per development area were purposefully delivered by the designated facilitators of the Fadama office to respondents

from the ten Fadama development areas in the six Area Councils. The test runs of the questionnaires were conducted before they were sent to randomly chosen groups and clusters on the farms. This was done to personally observe the rice crops.

Insect pest collection and identification

Farm insect samples were collected by catching live insects in a cup or other small container for other insects and using nets for

flying insects. After being carefully picked up, the insects were covered with a lid or a paper towel. All captured insects were given a date, location, and name label before being immediately put into 95% ethanol or rubbing alcohol (isopropyl). The collected insects were accurately identified using a guidebook for cereal insect pest identification or an online identification key guidebook for cereal insect pest identification, Insect morphospecies were also sorted using a microscope connected to a computer (Tuzun *et al.*, 2010).

Assessment of pest incidence

Rice samples were examined to see if they had any abnormalities like holes, spots, or

discoloration on the leaves, if the plants were smaller than usual, or if any sections of the plant were dead. We also looked for abnormalities like holes, spots, or discoloration in the stem or panicles/grains (Federico *et al.*, 2015).

In a farmer's field or store that was visited, the prevalence of pests was visually assessed at least three times (Anjorin *et al.*, 2020). According to Ogolla *et al.* (2019), percentage incidence was estimated as the number of infected crops stands over the overall number of crop stands sampled.

$$\text{Pest incidence} = \frac{\text{number of infested plant}}{\text{total number of sampled plants}} \times 100 \dots(1)$$

Statistical analysis

Data obtained from the two hundred and eighty (190) retrieved questionnaires were coded and inputted, and descriptive statistics such as frequencies, tables, and bar charts were obtained with Microsoft Excel version 2021. Most results including a personal interview and observation on the pest on the field were presented in frequency, percentages, pie chart and bar chart. The Plates of major insect pests, and weeds on rice fields are shown.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Rice production practices in the FCT

The farmers sourced seeds mainly from the FADAMA coordinator. About 93.17% planted FARO 44 variety while the remaining 6.83% planted local varieties. Only 12.93% planted on marshy Fadama land, 77.56% were planted on lowland and 12.93% used upland for their rice farms. The majority of the FCT farmers (25.33%) plant their rice in June of every year. It was indicated that 65.60% of the

rice farmers cultivated their rice on the same field used in the previous year, while 34.40% farmed on fallowed land. This implied that less croppable land are available for fallow and more fertilizer input might be required. Of the respondents who cultivated rice, 43.24% had a farm size of between 1 and 3 hectares (ha) mostly in Abaji and Kwali Area Councils, while 38.32% had below one hectare (Fig. 1).

As high as 92.00% of the rice farmers adopted monocropping. This indicated that crop rotation or mixed cropping was not commonly practiced by rice farmers and this cultural method is not often used for managing pests on the rice farm. Fadama extension agents should educate or train the farmers' on appropriate fertilization systems in a rice farm.

Fig. 1: Farm size of rice farmers of the FCT, Abuja

Challenges to Rice production in the FCT, Abuja

Majority (56.67%) of the farmers considered weeds as the most problematic pest on rice farm (Fig. 2). The adverse effects of weeds on rice was also reported by Agnoun *et al.* (2012) and Banjo *et al.* (2010).

Fig. 2: Challenges of Rice farming in the FCT, Abuja as indicated by the farmers

Incidence of insect pests in the FCT, Nigeria

From the diagnostic survey the mean incidence of armyworm infestation was

28.91%, African rice gall midge was 18.85%, and stem borer was 11.84% (Table 1). Other insect pests observed on the rice farms were rice bug, whorl maggot, termites, and leaf folders, but their incidence were not determined.

Table 1: Incidence by insect pests, associated with rice farms in the FCT.

S/No	Common name	Species	Incidence (%)
1	African rice gall midge	<i>Orzeola oryzivora</i>	18.85
2	Stem borer	<i>Chiloza cconius</i>	11.84
3	Whorl maggot	<i>Hydrellia spp</i>	-
4	Rice bug	<i>Aspervia armigera</i>	-
5	Army worm	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	28.91
6	Leaf folder	<i>Marasmis tapezalis</i>	-
7	Termites	<i>Macrotermes spp</i>	-

Some common insect pests of rice in the FCT are shown in the Plates 1-4. Army worm are caterpillars that prey on rice (Plate 1). They reside on the bottom of rice stands' leafy surfaces. The fall armyworm is well recognized for feeding on the leaves of young rice plants, causing significant tissue loss, trimming the seedlings to the ground, and severe stand loss. They also feed on leaf tips and leaf margins (Odeyemi *et al.*, 2020; Makgoba *et al.*, 2021). Stem borer (Plate 2) can destroy rice at any stage, from seedling to maturity. Its larvae can bore at the base of the plants during the vegetative stage, while they bore through the upper nodes and feed toward the base, on older plants (Adewoye *et al.*, 2021). Dead-hearts and whiteheads are symptoms of stem borer that may be confused with rat damage, neck blast and black bug diseases.

Whorl maggot – a rice leaf miner (Plate 3) is a semi-aquatic, commonly inhabits irrigated fields, and survives on the central whorl leaf of the vegetative stage of the rice plant. This rice pest does not occur in upland rice Rice whorl

maggots are tiny flies that range in color from grey to black and have markings on the lower part of their heads that range from silvery white to golden brown. These larvae feed on the leaf margins, leaving behind significant scarring that gives the leaf a ragged look and ultimately results in leaf collapse (Ogah and Nwilene, 2012). Eventually, the maggots locate the whorl and burrow into the growing system of the rice plant. A little, reddish-brown midge, the African rice gall midge is depicted on Plate 4. Light swellings or galls are brought on by the midge feeding as a larva, and these galls are typically not noticeable until the larvae are ready to pupate. According to research by Marti *et al.* (2009) and Sama *et al.* (2016), gall midge causes severe harm to rice plants from seedling through panicle initiation. The galls start to form 20 to 40 days after rice is transplanted. Galled plants may tiller excessively to make up for the loss of growth points in afflicted rice tillers, which do not form panicles. The rainy season is when they most frequently appear. They are midges and do not attack rice plants that have passed the tillering stage.

Incidence of weeds on rice farm in the FCT

A shallow-water and floodplain grassland weed, *Sacciolepis africana* (Plate 5) with a mean incidence of 28.18% (Table 2), was regarded as the most stubborn to control and observed to be tolerant to most herbicides. Sedge (*Cyperus rotundus*) had an incidence of 28.18% and was more

prevalent on a lowland rice farm. Goat weed (*Agerantum conyzoides*) had the lowest incidence of 6.68%. About 13.50% and 23.07% of the farmers combined indigenous knowledge systems such as spraying garlic extracts with synthetic insecticides respectively to control insect pests on a rice farm, and their level of effectiveness is believed to be moderate.

Table 2: Incidence of major weeds associated with rice on the farm

Nomenclature	Incidence (%)
Cupscale grass (<i>Sacciolepis africana</i>)	28.43
Wire grass (<i>Sporobolus diander</i>)	12.96
Goat weed (<i>Agerantum conyzoides</i>)	6.68
Sedge (<i>Cyperus todoratus</i>)	28.18
Wire grass (<i>Sporobolus diander</i>)	7.58
Purple chloris (<i>Chloris barbata</i>)	8.66
Crowfoot grass (<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i>)	31.77

Plate 5: *Sacciolepis africana* (Cupscale grass)

Table 3: Incidence of other pests associated with rice on the farm

Common name	Species	Incidence
Rodents	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	26.76
Cattle/goat	<i>Bos/Capra</i> spp	11.12
Bird pests	Quella spp, Weaver	28.24

Management of rice field pests in the FCT

About 30.33% used synthetic herbicides in clearing or managing weeds especially Roundup® during bush clearing. Up to

65.00% of the farmers used IPM in controlling rodents and mammal pests on their farm and indicated it had a high level of efficacy (Table 4).

Table 4: Management of mammalian pests (Grasscutter, Cattle, Goat, Rat) on rice farm in the FCT

Management method	Percentage (%) of users
indigenous knowledge/Manual/organic killer/nets against birds	27.55
synthetic pesticide	7.45
PM	65.00

CONCLUSION

From this study, it was indicated that Armyworm is the most common insect pest on rice farms in the FCT. This insect pest had the highest incidence of 28.91% and was used to reduce yield significantly. About 56.67% of rice farmers considered weeds as the greatest constraint of rice farming in the FCT.

Sacciolepis africana, is said to be the most stubborn to control using herbicides, as it has the most tolerance level. A field experiment where the impact of the insects and weed infestation on the yield can be determined is necessary. The FADAMA extension agents need to educate the farmers more on Integrated Pests Management (IPM) practices.

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